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Abstract

After the collapse of the Goyturk Empire, two independent states were formed in the territories of Eastern Europe and the North Caucasus. These states were the states of the Great Bulgars and the Khazars. Both states, competing with each other from the first period of their existence, weakened. As a result, the Great Bulgarian State was divided. The Khazars eventually became stronger and subjugated the surrounding regions. The Bulgarians, moving in different directions, created two independent states in different periods. The Bulgarians settled in the Volga-Kama region and accepted the political power of the Khazars. The Khazars became more powerful, expanding their traditions of statehood, the Khazars participated as intermediaries in trade between Europe and Asia. Like all nomadic federations of that time, the state of the Khazars weakened and disintegrated. After the Khazars gained independence, the Bulgarians further developed their society and existed for several centuries.

Keywords: Khazars, Bulgars, Khagan, Nomads, Islam, Judaism, Tengirism.

In the initial historical period of its existence in the Caspian kaganate, it had all the features of the kharterik for the nomadic Turkic societies that existed in the Eurasian steppes before. Khazar tribes came to the territory of Eastern Europe during the Great Migration of peoples (IV-VII centuries). The Khazars were subordinate to the Turkic kaganate for some time. In the Byzantine-Sassanid wars of 602-628, the Khazars took part as the main ally of the Byzantine Empire. During the wars, the Khazars received large military booty. In addition, in exchange for their alliance, the Byzantine State paid them a huge amount of money [15.43]. After the Khazars plundered Caucasian Albania (in 627), together with the Byzantines, they captured the city of Tiflis. Soon the Turkic kaganate completely collapsed, and two nomadic Confederate Empires arose on its western lands. One of these states was the great Bulgar state, which arose in the north eastern Black Sea region. Kubrat Khan founded the Bulgar state in 632. The second state that arose was the Khazar state, which arose in the steppes surrounding the Caspian. After the death of Kubrat Khan, the great Bulgar state created by him was divided into five parts between his boys. In the first wars with the Khazars, the Bulgars had to migrate from their territories, as they were defeated. [3.12] one of these Bulgar groups, under the leadership of Asparukh Khan, settled in the lower reaches of the Danube and established a new state here. Other groups retreat to the steppes around the Don River. Another group went to Italy and settled in the province of Campania. the fourth group of Bulgars moved to the lands of the avar kaganate and settled in central Europe. The remaining Bulgar tribes accepted the rule of the Khazars and remained in their inhabited territories. From the middle of the VII century, the Khazars controlled the steppes to the west of the Volga and began to bear the title of Khagan, the Lord of the Khazar state. After the Khazars consolidated their power, a period of re-stabilization comes to the steppes of Eastern Europe. They stop the influx of new nomadic groups from Asia into

Europe, and they themselves create stable relations with their sedentary neighbors. The Khazars traded mainly with Byzantine possessions located in the Crimea and Dagestan territory in which they were sedentary and was engaged in viticulture [19]. With all this, the basis of the economy of the Khazars was nomadic cattle breeding. It was considered one of the income-generating areas in plundering campaigns, which was considered a source of income for nomadic tribes. Continuing the alliance with Byzantium, the Khazars helped Byzantium in stopping the Arabs in Asia Minor. They played an important role in the fact that in 716-718 the siege of Constantinople by the troops of the caliphate ended in failure. The Khazars once again attacked Caucasian Albania and surrounded part of the Arab Army and plundered the area again. In 730-731. The Khazars advanced deep into the Lands of the Caliphate. they routed the 25-thousandth Arab Army on the territory of Chimali Mosul [12].131]. After Marwan, an experienced commander, stopped the Khazar offensive, he launched a counteroffensive against them. He entered the territory of the Caspian Sea with an army of 120 thousand people. The city of Samandar, which is believed to be on the territory of Northern Dagestan, was captured. Samandar was located on the coast of the Caspian Sea. Marwan, the commander who captured Samandar, pursued the Khagan and advanced towards the steppes surrounding the Khazar Khazars defeated in ardar, began peace negotiations peace was concluded in return for Khagn's acceptance of the terms of the Arab commander. One condition of peace was that the Khagan converted to islam, while the Khagan converted to Islam. The Arab threat to the Khazars has passed. Marwan returned to the South. In later times, the Caliphate no longer claimed the North Caucasus. The actual transition of the Kagan to Islam did not take place, but the consequences of the Arab invasion turned out to be extremely significant for the Khazars [5]. The Khazars themselves retreated from the North Caucasus along the Volga Don to the North East. They built the

city of Itil with their new capital in the Volga Delta . The former capital city of Samandar remained on the southern border . In subsequent periods, there is also a gradual change in the socio-economic orientation of the population of the kaganate. In the northern Black Sea steppes and the Volga-Don River, in its southern part (in Crimea, in Taman), farming based on nomadic cattle breeding is of great importance in it . Part of the Khazars are moving to sedentary agricultural life in Northern Dagestan and in the north on the Middle Volga and in the Kama region [19.121] . By controlling the mouth of the Caspian Sea from the forest zone of the Volga, the Khazars take control of the northern and Southern trade artery. The importance of the Volga is growing sharply due to the unprecedented expansion of the Arab Caliphate, which has created a vast trading space and market for Northern furs, honey, wax and linen from the Caucasus and Central Asia to the Indian Ocean . The Caspian state, whose Volga trade has increasingly turned from a typical nomadic steppe Confederation into an early state, serves as a kind of bridge connecting isolated communities of the northern regions and peoples with a developed culture . The Arabs ' attempt to convert the Khazars to Islam was also quite significant. Like most nomads of the Central Asian steppes of the 1st millennium AD (regardless of "ethnic" or linguistic affiliation) . In the Khazars, they believed in the religion of Tengrism . They believed in the Supreme God, The Eternal Sky (Tengri), the Sacred Earth-Water and no less significant gods, personifying the forces of nature. Tengrianism was the common value of nomadic peoples . Tengirism was considered the main factor uniting the nomadic Turkic peoples . However, Tengirism did not represent such a rigid and complex cultural system as monotheistic religions. With the complication and development of society, single God-based religions seemed increasingly attractive among the nomadic population . The transition to new religions resulted in a further strengthening of society and the power of the ruler . The Arab crushing of the Khagan's army on the territory of the Khazars resulted in the transformation of religion from a cultural and ideological issue into a key political factor . In 737 volumes, very few of the Khazars professed Islam . In 740, The Great Khazar commander, belonging to the ruling elite, Bulan, along with members of his subordinate tribe, converted to the Jewish religion . Judaism was adopted by the ruling class of the Khazars . the Buddha, in turn, was one of the main reasons for the disintegration of the Khazar society in subsequent periods . The transitional nature of the Khazar kaganate was manifested in the fact that the emergence of a new religion and worldview did not lead to the change and destruction of the old, but, on the contrary, reconciled with it. Thus, having moved the capital to ITIL, the Khazars did not leave Samandar, but simply changed its status. The development of trade and Agriculture did not result in a complete abandonment of nomadic cattle breeding [17 .61] . The conversion of Bulan and some ruling classes to Judaism did not mean radical religious reform. All confessions lived together in the Khazar kaganate. The territory of Crimea was inhabited mainly by

people of Christian and previous religions . Khristianism spread throughout Dagestan . Islam mainly included members of the army . And the Kagan himself remained the embodiment of the divine power of tengiri . In the southern regions, there were fertile conditions for the development of nomadic cattle breeding . In the Bulgar steppes, herds of horse herons and al Gara grazed, which would provide the population . It was strongly developed in agriculture . Here mainly: wheat, barley, millet, lentils and beans were grown . In addition to the grain trade carried out with the Bulgars, in The Chronicles of the pre-Mongol invasion, requests for grain from neighboring states during the years of famine and drought are mentioned . the Buddha, in turn, testifies to the high development of grain growing. The provision of the necessary food products in the country resulted in the number of the population . the Buddha led to the emergence and development of State inistuts . The transition of the people to a sedentary life the receipt of taxes from the entire population, and not from subordinate tribes, was an indicator that the state was developing and moving to a new stage of development . The gradual spread of Islam among the population (which had to take decades) created a common social space, where differences (languages, lines of kinship) were equalized, which was an urgent problem between tribes. . With the proclamation of Islam as the official state religion in the Volga Bulgar state, the subsequent suvar and Khazar typhalr with ethnic Bulgars were united by other Finno-Ugric Peoples, which accelerated the formation of a single Bulgar people . In 737, the Khazars converted to Islam [8]. After the defeat of the kaganate by the troops of the Arab Caliphate (as promised to the victors), there would be nothing new and unusual in this. Many peoples conquered by the Arabs or under their influence converted to Islam. The issue of interest is that after 740, the Khazar tribal nobility adopted Judaism, another monotheistic religion, on their own initiative, which in Judaism there was no tradition of preaching their religion among members of other religions (prozeltizim) . Almost a century and a half later, history repeats itself again in the field of religious references on the northern periphery of the Khazar kaganate . In 922, the Volga Bulgars established contacts with the distant Baghdad caliphate on the basis of their aspirations and adopted Islam as the official religion. [8.56] it is known that some Muslim population of the Khazar kaganate lived, Muslims could also be on the territory of the Bulgars , but the question of whether the initiative to accept Islam as a religion came from the Bulgars themselves, and not from outside propagandists, is important . The adoption of monotheistic religions in the Khazar kaganate and the Bulgar state developed on the basis of the same trend . Such a way of choosing between the new religions was applied in the Russian state, which was its neighbors, so Prince Vladimir of Kiev chose between the monotheistic religions, while Bulgars recommended Islam to him Khazars Judaism and Byzantium recommended khristianism . The Russians adopted khristian provocation . Similarly, before the adoption of Judaism by the Khazars , a discussion between representatives of the three monotheistic confessions was held, in which Muslims

claimed the superiority of Islam over Christianity, and Christians-the opposite, but the acceptance of Judaism as the “most correct” religion after them by both members of the confesians resulted in the Khazars' focus on Judaism .During the period of the fires dependent on the Khazar khagnlg and later, the country of the Volga Bulls was in a geographical position favorable for trade. It was in Bua that the Middle Ages crossed the most important roads of Eastern Europe and Asia, stretching from North to South and from West to East thanks to the Volga and Kama rivers .the location in such a favorable area helped not only intermediary trade, but also the development of Bulgarian crafts, which turned the product into a commodity.[13.11] The development of craft production in the Caspian and bulgar cities required the organized placement of industrial complexes so as not to disturb the safety and comfort of life of residents. First of all, this applies to crafts associated with the use of fire (metallurgy, blacksmithing, ceramic production). Artisan workshops were mainly built on the outskirts of the city .. In some cases, a sanitary zone was introduced around these facilities. For the storage of waste from workshops , special pits were dug, in addition, the leveling of streets (filling pits, ravines, etc.) was made from these materials.) could have been used for. The interests of organizing crafts and minimizing its impact on the urban environment also led to the transformation of shops-workshops into large closed markets, where trade was carried out in parallel with production .The archaeological report of the Khazar Khaganate shows that the main reason for the collapse of the country's economy was caused by sharp climatic changes . At the beginning of the X century. In the north of Eastern Europe, heavy rains fell for quite a long time, which ultimately led to a rise in the water level of the Caspian Sea. As a result of this natural disaster, the fields, pastures and fishing farms of the Khazars were flooded. As a result of a natural disaster, the economy of the Khanate collapsed. The khazarsthey lost two-thirds of the territory of their fertile territory and, as a result, all their wealth [17.113]. After that, the Khazars lived at the expense of taking full control of the Caspian trade route .But this does not mean that the Khazar kaganate was in complete decline . During the reign of the Khazar Khagan Yusuf (X 40 - 60s), the state of the Khazars, surrounded on all sides by numerous hostile tribes and states, could still defend itself, although it had lost its former greatness ..Unlike the Khazars, the Volga Bulgars were in a better position economically . Bulgar at the beginning of the X century . the basis of its economy was agriculture, craft production and diversified trade, which was quite developed for its time. The Arab geographer and traveler Ibn-Ruste wrote that “the Bulgarians are a farming people and cultivate all kinds of cereals (wheat, barley, millet, etc.) .) .In addition to agriculture, livestock was of great importance in the economy of the Bulgars, which acted as a source of raw materials for crafts, primarily leather and bone carving. Bulgarian boots, nicknamed "Bulgari", were very popular in the East [8 .12].

Unlike the Caspian, the inhabitants of the Volga Bulgar were skillful senettkars, and its products were

also an important export product. The products of Bulgarian masters, especially jewelry, were used among the peoples of the North and Perm Territory as an exchange equivalent of Sable, Marten, Beaver and ermine fur, which was expensive in the East. The growth of trade with Eastern countries led to the formation of Eastern technologies of the Bulgars , and after them-scientists who contributed to the development of local culture . The obstacles imposed by the Khazar Khaganate to the development of the Bulgar economy displeased local nobles and merchants . The coming tsirs, who were forced to pay heavy taxes to the Khazars, were interested in strengthening the Bulgar state . But this could guarantee the safety of their trade, trade routes and the “development of commodity-money relations.” Bulgar Elvati Almas paid a tenth of his income as a tax to the Khazars . Elteber's desire to marry the daughter of the Kagan failed .From the middle of the X century, the Khazar state was going through a political crisis Kiev kinyazi Sveteslav attacked the Khazar state in 965, having tied up with nomadic tribes opposed to the Khazars, and the capital city was captured . Khagan was forced to ask for help from the Kharazim order[19.44] . After that, the Khazars were completely saved from destruction . Against the background of these events, all Khazars, except for the Khagan family and a small ruling class, professed islam .The collapse of the Khazar state resulted in the Bulgars gaining full independence . Having become independent, the Bulgars occupied the lands belonging to the Khazar Kaganate around them and expanded their territories . In later periods, most Khazar tribes moved to the territory of the Bulgar state and settled there . new arrivals began to engage in agricultural farming with blight [19.44]. They gradually mixed with the Bulgars, going into a sedentary life . Until the Mongol invasion, the Bulgars and the Russians fought for hegemony in Eastern Europe . they were different periods, even if one side prevailed over the other . None of the parties was able to fully win . As a result of this rivalry and lack of trust in each other, the Mongols easily defeated the Russians and Bulgars .

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